

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMERCIAL SERVICES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the use of effective methods of trade services, the development of a strategy for its new forms and methods of production. Practical application of various self-service technologies to optimize the trade and technological process abroad. The effectiveness of commercial reconciliation is associated with the development of information technologies designed to simplify the elimination of the consequences of the purchase.*

Keywords: *strategy, international trade, innovative technologies, consumer goods, information, retail trade.*

ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ РАЗВИТИЯ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ УСЛУГ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается использование эффективных методов торгового обслуживания, разработка стратегии его новых форм и методов производства. Практическое применение различных технологий самообслуживания для оптимизации торгово-технологического процесса за рубежом. Эффективность коммерческого примирения связана с развитием информационных технологий, призванных упростить ликвидацию последствий покупки.*

Ключевые слова: *стратегия, международная торговля, инновационные технологии, товары народного потребления, информация, розничная торговля.*

INTRODUCTION Today, there is a large foreign experience in the development of trade services, and increasing the volume of trade through the use of various methods of trade services is becoming important in the development of the enterprise. Based on Jaxon's experience, more and more innovative technologies will be used in the sales process in the implementation of strategic goals such as capturing new markets and increasing the company's market share.

Made in the conditions of innovative development of the Republic of Uzbekistan a new economy that is emerging on the basis of increasing priority economic reforms relationships, modern forms of service and based on the use of methods opens wide opportunities to increase the efficiency of trade services. Socio-economic development, development of techniques and technologies, in particular, life in the Republic material and spiritual needs of the population as well as improving their well-being is observed to increase.

International that is implemented in the world the development of trade along with capital movement and tourism affects the economic growth rates of countries. New As a result of reforms carried out in Uzbekistan, openness, development of international economic and political relations create opportunities for modernization, technical and technological re-equipment of the system of trade networks in our country.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Socio-economic development, the development of techniques and technologies, in particular, the life of the Uzbek people material and spiritual needs of the population as well as improving their well-being serves to increase. The reforms implemented in Uzbekistan improve the efficiency of the national economy aimed at increasing. Trade is a part of the "Market", which is a structural and integral part of the market economy as a branch of consumer goods production to consumers performs the perfect function of conveying

through the process. In the trading process, all elements of the market take part in supply, price and demand. These elements are coordinated through competition in trade.

It is necessary to emphasize that from the scientific, socio-economic point of view in scientific works, educational and popular There are different academic views on trade and markets in the literature.

In this regard, the world's leading marketer F. Kotler [1] calls the place where trade is carried out - the market "a complex of existing and potential buyers of goods." describes. Also, another group of major economists in the Dune, K.R. McConnell and S.L. Brewer, defined market and trade, product and service as interconnected components, seller and buyers are called adding mechanisms.[2]

A.S. Usmanov, one of the leading economists, defines trade as a component of the market: "The concept of market and trade is broad in the sense that it is the field of commodity exchange, as long as there is commodity exchange, the market and trade also exists," he says. [3]. In this regard, American scientist P. Samuelson's work "Economics" describes the market - "... markets are society and trade appears as a mechanism connecting production activities", he describes [4].

According to N. Tukhlievni, one of the economists of the republic, "The market is organized on the basis of the laws of production of goods Trade is a sum of exchange, commodity and money circulation relations, it is an important link between production and consumption" [5].

B. Abdukarimov from Uzbek scientists""Planning, first of all, is defining the future and choosing promising directions for increasing its effectiveness."[6] M.Pardaev" The process of reproduction in society moves through the following factors: The first factor is the human factor, his work; the second factor is the means of labor, i.e. capital; the third factor is natural resources, land; the fourth factor is entrepreneurship" [7], I.Ivatov" In trade, economic laws that develop society are reflected. Therefore, on the basis of trade management, it is necessary to be able to objectively see the requirements of economic laws and make decisions based on them. should get

In general, activities in the process of extended reproduction (production, distribution, exchange and consumption), including trade, are defined as "[9] such scientists have carried out in-depth studies on the evolution of trade services and the problems of trade development in modern market relations. Sh.Shodmonov, M.Rakhmatov, one of the leading scientists of the republic ("Economic Theory" Higher Education textbook for countries, Tashkent. "Zamin Nashrah", 2021) opinions in this regard are of particular note.

They point out that "the complex of relations between market-producers and consumers (sellers and buyers) in the process of exchange through money" and especially in this process "... industrial goods store, sales branches of merchants, various supermarkets, large shopping centers and trade fairs , restaurants are typical market features" [10].

Research methodology.This study included the tasks of the trade system, its content, its theoretical and methodological foundations, and its place in the economic and social spheres. The article uses methods of observation, comparison, theoretical and practical study, and statistical analysis. The analyzed data and indicators are the result of in-depth analytical data in the research work.

Analysis and results.Various self-service technologies are widely used to provide sales service and optimize the technological process abroad. Technologies of trade services based on

the experiences of the leading countries of the world (price checker, information kiosk, self-service cash register, radio frequency signs (RFID technology), "personal" assistant of buyers, "intelligent" virtual assistant system based on the ability to attract consumers and reduce costs in stores. These experiences open very important and new opportunities in the trade system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Improving the efficiency of the sales process is connected with the development of information technologies, which made it possible to further simplify the purchase process. Price checkers are currently not widely used in Uzbekistan to improve the efficiency of trade services. It should be noted separately that price checkers from CIS countries, especially Belarus, use the technology of trade services widely. Through this sales service device, buyers have the opportunity to determine the prices of goods without the help of employees, and systematic sales are established [11].

An information kiosk from sales service technologies is a multifunctional electronic device with a touch screen designed to provide access to various information resources [12]. The main function of this self-service technology is to provide detailed information about the product. Information kiosks are successfully used by various German companies in Germany.

The information kiosk completely replaces the paper catalogs used in enterprises. Information about the scanned product can be supplemented with reminders about promotions and sales running in this store. The final price can be calculated by taking into account the discounts applicable to the buyer.

Self-service checkouts are technologies that allow customers to scan, bag, and pay for items themselves without the help of store staff. It should be noted separately that such service technologies were first implemented in Germany by the Metro Group retail chain in 300 stores, that is, they introduced self-service checkouts. This technology increases customer interest in the store and attracts innovative consumers who have complete control over the purchase process without the intervention of retailers. The possibility of misappropriation of goods by employees, as well as acceptance of counterfeit banknotes and coins, is prevented. However, the possibility of such a situation remains on the part of buyers, because the buyer may not be able to scan the purchased product, therefore, certain safety precautions are required. According to most employees, this technology helps to ease the work of employees during the busiest hours and increase the hours of store hours. New cash registers were also used in other companies operating in the German market (Edeka, Ikea, etc.).

Radio frequency tags (RFID technologies) replace modern barcodes, which allow the customer to instantly calculate the price of the shopping cart. This contactless device can operate at a distance of up to 1.5 m and can read hundreds of characters simultaneously using a scanner [13]. Currently, RFID tags are actively introduced in Germany. According to Deutsche Bank, the average annual growth rate of RFID technology turnover was 19%. It is worth noting that these technologies are already used in various projects by retail chains such as Metro, Karstadt, Reve and Harry Weber. If the goods are marked with RFID tags, the customer collects the goods with a cart and takes it through a special turnstile at the checkout.

The personal assistant of the buyer (PSA), which is widely used in the German trade system, is a special device based on a special digitized system, with the help of which the buyer independently scans the bar codes of the goods he is interested in during the purchase process, the display shows the latest information about products and promotions. In addition, the personal

assistant is often activated by the customer's club card, so it can display a list of past purchases made by the consumer, making the shopping process even easier[14]. In Germany, this equipment is still used in a number of stores, in particular, in the Dohle retail chain and the Metro chain. This allowed companies to cross-sell and offer the consumer exactly what he was interested in. In addition,

The experience of developed countries in the field of trade shows that the process of updating and modernizing the material and technical base of the industry and improving trade processes has accelerated. Retail trade remains the main form of selling goods in modern conditions. It should be noted that, according to the above, various technical innovations, along with the choice of forms and methods of selling goods, are gaining great importance in the effective organization of sales and customer service. This is due to the need for trade organizations to constantly gain competitive advantages in order to maintain and strengthen their position in the market. Currently, there are many examples of innovations in retail organizations (price check, information kiosk, self-service checkout,

In Western countries, mobile commerce has become a developed industry of personal commerce. A significant part of the sales is carried out by employees of independent agents, who may also be engaged in sales part-time (less than 30 hours per week). Independent agents do not receive a salary from specialized firms, but are distributors who buy goods from these firms and distribute them to consumers.

In Western European countries, consignment (parcel) trade has risen to a high level: its share in the total volume of sales of goods reaches 5-6%, and in individual assortment 15-30%[16]. This form of retailing is used for a wide range of food and non-food products. There are cases where specialized mail order firms open traditional retail stores. The main purpose of such stores is to sell unsold goods by mail. At the same time, they contribute to activating the role of mail order trade in local commodity markets, attracting additional buyers. In France, mail order firms sell goods through three channels for orders from the public: by mail, including e-mail, by telephone,

International experience shows that first of all, it is an urgent issue for trade to find effective methods of providing trade services and to solve the problems of further increasing the level of service to the population. For this purpose, new forms of trade and methods of selling goods are being introduced. Among the new forms of trade, for example, Cash & carry, stock trading, second hand - these forms are still not well developed in Uzbekistan. Thus, the advantages of stores operating on the Cash & Carry technology include the availability and mobility of goods, as well as the ability to provide almost any order in terms of size and assortment without requiring much time from the customer. Stock trading not sold (producers, sellers) are carried out by structures that buy a lot of leftover goods and arrange to sell them at reduced prices. At the same time, in the West, such structures cooperate at all stages of the creation and sale of goods, from the production of raw materials to the retail network. In fact, these structures perform a regulatory function, help the manufacturer to eliminate the consequences of overproduction, sellers to get rid of excess goods, and buyers to buy goods with a minimum margin.

Currently, various technical innovations are of great importance, along with the work of service personnel, in improving the service culture. This experience has become a unique aspect of German stores, and the central place in the strategy of the development of trade stores is given

to an individual approach to each consumer. The main task of this direction is not to increase store or network sales, but to increase the volume of sales during communication with each of the customers[17]. In order to create a group of "loyal" customers, it is becoming popular for stores to distribute special club cards free of charge to customers who visit the store several times.

It should be noted separately that the sale of consumer goods in developed countries is carried out in two directions: firstly, as a form of additional service to customers from stationary stores, and secondly, as an independent form of trade activity[18]. In the first case, order departments are established in supermarkets, which receive orders by phone and deliver them to customers' homes at a certain time. In the second case, specialized order stores are created. In some countries (USA, France) there are specialized firms with a chain of custom stores.

In the sale of non-food products, order sales and sample sales are common in the United States, Germany, England, France, and some other countries. In this case, the TV screen serves as a means of offering goods. The screen not only shows the product, but also notes its advantages, possibilities of use, price. After choosing the product, the customer places an order by phone or PC. In turn, the trading company sends the ordered goods by mail or provides delivery in another way. The sale of goods can be carried out through public television channels or cable television.

The sale of goods through vending machines is also widely developed in foreign countries. Vending machines are widely used in industrial enterprises for the organization of intermediate meals, where 15-20% of the total catering turnover is sold in this way. Vending of non-food products through vending machines is also developing to some extent. They are installed in shop windows, hotels, stations, subways (selling men's shirts, jeans, hats, haberdashery, books, newspapers, magazines).

It is known from foreign experience that the rapid development of trade through automatic machines, the use of modern forms of payment for goods using a debit or credit card helps to increase the efficiency of trade services [19]. The advantages of this calculation are as follows:

- simplifying the purchase process;
- ease of changing the price of goods (the price does not depend on the denomination of coins and banknotes);
- reducing the risk of income theft;
- the costs of collection and transportation of coins and banknotes are not charged;
- simplification of accounting and reporting.

In recent years, foreign practice of e-commerce has been developing rapidly. In this, many companies are focusing on increasing the types of trade services. In this regard, separate departments are being formed in the organizational structure of enterprises for the implementation and offering of non-traditional services (cleaning service, anniversary, video recording of weddings, home heating services, etc.).

Therefore, the provision of trade services is an integral part of the activities of trading firms not only in Germany, the USA and other developed countries, but also in other industrially developing countries. Sales services are aimed at helping customers acquire, transport and use goods to better meet demand and increase profits. Therefore, it is appropriate to carefully study

the experience of foreign countries and apply it in the practice of trade enterprises of our republic.

Conclusions and suggestions.

It is necessary to develop the legal basis of trade services and eliminate many economic problems associated with further expansion and improvement of this sector. Based on the above, on the basis of the foreign experience of the development of trade services, it is necessary to give priority to the following in the development of these services in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Including:

1. In the practice of trade services, systematic organization of the placement of goods in accordance with the assortment of goods intended for sale, based on the demand of buyers, characteristic of the national mentality of the republic.
2. Relying on the global experience in providing trade services, paying special attention to the study of customer psychology by special specialist employees, and on this basis, organizing trade areas based on a special design.
3. Taking into account the traditions and customs of buyers in the places where the goods are sold, and organizing sales platforms and processes based on the corresponding foreign practices.
4. Today, in the leading developed countries of the world, the provision of trade services is based on the technologies of sales platforms, which are based on the characteristics, density, assortment of goods for sale, etc.

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